

Breaching the Defense: Investigating FGSM and CTGAN Adversarial Attacks on IEC 60870-5-104 AI-enabled Intrusion Detection Systems

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ABSTRACT

In the digital age of the hyper-connected Critical Infrastructures (CIs), the role of the smart electrical grid is crucial, providing several benefits, such as improved grid resilience, efficient energy distribution and smart load and response management. However, despite the several advantages, the rapid evolution of the heterogeneous technologies involved in the smart electrical grid increases the attack surface. In this paper, we focus first our attention on how Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be used to protect the smart electrical grid in terms of detecting efficiently potential cyberattacks and anomalies. Secondly, we investigate how AI can be used to trick AI-enabled detection services, thus resulting in false alarms. In particular, we emphasise on cyberattacks against IEC 60870-5-104, an industrial communication protocol which is widely used in the energy domain. Therefore, a relevant AI-powered Intrusion Detection System (IDS) is provided, utilising strong Machine Learning (ML)/Deep Learning (DL) methods, such as Decision Tree, Random Forest, XGBOOST and deep MultiLayer Perceptron (MLP). On the other hand, we investigate how adversarial attacks can affect the detection performance of the previous IDS. For this purpose, the Fast Gradient Signed Method (FGSM) is examined, and a Conditional Tabular Generative Adversarial Network (CTGAN) adversarial attack generator is implemented. The evaluation results demonstrate the efficiency of the proposed IDS and the aforementioned adversarial attacks.

CCS CONCEPTS

• Security and privacy → Intrusion detection systems.

KEYWORDS

Adversarial Attacks, Artificial Intelligence, Cybersecurity, Generative Adversarial Networks, Intrusion Detection

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1 INTRODUCTION

Technology enablers, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), 5G and Artificial Intelligence (AI), play a significant role in the lifecycle of Critical Infrastructures (CIs), such as the smart electrical grid. Characteristic benefits are environmental sustainability, resource optimisation and improved reliability. However, this revolution raises severe cybersecurity issues that can result in disastrous consequences, especially in the energy domain[4]. In particular, multi-step attack scenarios and Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs) against critical infrastructures (such as the smart electrical grid) can result in various cascading effects with widespread service outages, financial losses, or even fatal accidents. Characteristic examples of APT [2] campaigns are Indostroyer, SolarWinds (Sunburst), Hafnium and the Lazarus Group. Indostroyer resulted in a large-scale blackout in Ukraine in 2015. Another characteristic cybersecurity incident was the NotPetya ransomware, which affected several energy-related organisations in terms of financial losses. In addition, AI can further evolve the cyberattacks in terms of automating

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and adjusting them in order to mislead potential countermeasures. Therefore, it is obvious that the presence of appropriate and continuously adaptable detection and mitigation mechanisms is more necessary than ever. AI can also play a significant defensive role in the operation of detection mechanisms, allowing the recognition of zero-day cyberattacks and unknown anomalies. However, AI-powered detection systems are prone to false alarms and can be threatened by adversarial attacks that aim to violate the accuracy of the statistical analysis and AI detection models [6].

In this paper, we focus first our attention on the implementation of an AI-powered Intrusion Detection System (IDS) against cyberattacks that target the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol. Although IEC 60870-5-104 is widely used in Industrial IoT (IIoT) applications, especially in the energy sector, it is characterised by severe security issues since it does not incorporate any authentication and access control mechanisms, thus allowing potential cyberattacker(s) to execute Man-In-The-Middle (MITM) and unauthorised activities [9]. For this purpose, various AI methods are used in terms of Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) models, such as Decision Tree, XGBOOST, Random Forest and Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP). Second, we investigate adversarial evasion attacks against the aforementioned AI models. In particular, we emphasise on the Fast Gradient Sign Method (FGSM) and how Conditional Tabular Generative Adversarial Networks (CTGAN) can be used to synthesise adversarial attacks against the previous AI detection models. Therefore, based on the aforementioned remarks, the contributions of this paper are summarised as follows.

- **AI-Powered Intrusion Detection System (IDS) against IEC 60870-5-104 Attacks:** An AI-powered IDS is provided in terms of detecting and mitigating various cyberattacks against the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol. For this purpose, four ML/DL models (Decision Tree, XGBOOST, Random Forest and MLP) are used and compared with each other.
- **Investigating FGSM Adversarial Attacks:** We investigate how FGSM evasion adversarial attacks can affect the detection performance of the previous ML/DL models.
- **Development of CTGAN Adversarial Attack Generator:** We implement an adversarial attack generator that takes full advantage of FGSM and CTGAN.

The rest of this paper is organised as follows. Section 2 presents a background and similar works in this field. In section 3, our AI-powered IDPS against IEC 60870-5-104 attacks is described. Section 4 focuses on the FGSM evasion attacks and the development of the CTGAN adversarial attack generator. Finally, section 5 focuses on the evaluation analysis and experimental results, while section 6 concludes this paper.

2 BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

According to D. Denning in [3], the reference architecture of an IDS consists of three main components: (a) Agents, (b) Detection Engine and (c) Response Module. The agents are responsible for monitoring the underlying infrastructure by collecting the necessary data that will be utilised for the detection process. Next, the detection engine uses this data in order to detect potential cyberattacks or anomalies. In particular, there are two main categories of IDS in terms of their detection techniques: (a) signature/specification-based IDPS and (b)

anomaly-based IDPS. The first category uses pre-defined security rules that can identify specific malicious patterns, while, in the second category, statistical analysis and AI models are utilised for the detection process. Characteristic examples of both categories are provided in [7, 11, 12]. Finally, based on the detection outcomes, the response module notifies the user about the presence of cyberattacks and/or anomalies and activates potential countermeasures.

Therefore, according to the previous remarks, in [10], P. Radoglou-Grammatikis et al. present a threat model about IEC 60870-5-104, utilising a Coloured Petri Net (CPN). In particular, the authors focus on four cyberattacks against IEC 60870-5-104, namely: (a) unauthorised access, (b) MITM, (c) traffic analysis attacks and Denial of Service (DoS). IEC 60870-5-104 is an industrial communication protocol which is commonly adopted by Industrial Control Systems (ICS)/Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) environments. It uses, by default, the 2404 port of the Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) and does not include any authentication and authorisation mechanisms, thus allowing the previous attacks. Next, the authors in [5] present an anomaly-based Intrusion Detection System (IDS) that uses outlier detection mechanisms in order to recognise network anomalies related to IEC 60870-5-104. The proposed IDS consists of five modules: (a) Network Traffic Monitoring Module, (b) Network Packet Access Control Module, (c) Flows Extraction Module, (d) Anomaly Detection Module and (e) Response Module. The first module is responsible for capturing the IEC 60870-5-104 packets. The second module executes essential access control mechanisms in terms of the IP addresses and the TCP port. The Flows Extraction Module uses the CICFlowMeter in order to generate bidirectional flow statistics that are related to the IEC 60870-5-104 network traffic. Next, the Anomaly Detection Module undertakes to recognise potential anomalies based on the previous flow statistics, investigating three outlier detection algorithms: OneClass Support Vector Machine (SVM), Local Outlier Factor and Isolation Forest. Finally, the Notification Module notifies the user about the presence of security events. Finally, in [9] extend the previous work by investigating specific cyberattacks against IEC 60870-5-104, including (a) MITM, (b) DoS, (c) Traffic Sniffing and (d) various application-layer attacks related to the operational commands of IEC 60870-5-104. For the detection process, a Decision Tree is utilised, while Software-Defined Networking (SDN) is used to mitigate the attacks. Based on this work, the authors provided the first release of the IEC 60870-5-104 Intrusion Detection Dataset^{1,2}.

On the other hand, adversarial attacks are intentional, malicious attempts to deceive or control ML/DL models by exploiting inherent flaws. They entail making small and undetectable changes to the original input data so that the model will generate inaccurate predictions. Based on the knowledge the attackers have about the target system, the adversarial attacks can be categorised into three main classes, (a) white-box, (b) grey-box and (c) black-box attacks. In the white-box attacks, the adversary has complete knowledge of the target model, including the model's parameters, training data, and architecture. Therefore, the attacker can use sophisticated methods to generate adversarial input data. White-box attacks can

¹<https://iee-dataport.org/documents/iec-60870-5-104-intrusion-detection-dataset>

²<https://zenodo.org/record/7108614#.ZGTFktjBwxM>

take advantage of the model’s gradients to repeatedly optimise the perturbations that are applied to the input data, ensuring that they have the greatest possible influence on the model’s predictions. In a black-box attack, the adversary is unaware of the parameters or inner workings of the ML/DL model that is being attacked. They have only access to the input and output of the model. By examining the input-output relationship, the attacker approaches the model as a black box and creates adversarial examples. Black-box attacks frequently use query-based techniques, in which the adversary engages the model by submitting requests and monitoring the results. In a grey-box attack, the attackers have some limited knowledge of the model that is being attacked, such as the model’s architecture but not the model’s precise parameters or training data. This restricted knowledge is used by grey-box attackers to produce adversarial examples. They might use transferability, which is the ability to successfully transfer adversarial instances produced for a different model to the intended model. Finally, the adversarial attacks can also be grouped as poisoning attacks or evasion attacks. A classic poisoning attack involves injecting erroneous or falsified samples into the training dataset, which the model utilises to learn. These examples may have minute adjustments or carefully produced features intended to mislead the model during training. The purpose is to impact the model’s learning process so that it will generate inaccurate predictions or behave in an unexpected manner when used in real-world circumstances. In contrast, the goal of an evasion attack is to manipulate the input in such a way that the model misclassifies the perturbed sample while the changes made to the input are imperceptible to human observers. These adversarial examples are carefully crafted to exploit vulnerabilities in the model’s decision boundary and exploit its weaknesses.

In light of the previous remarks, in [8], N. Martins et al. provide a systematic review of adversarial attacks against intrusion and malware detection systems. In particular, the authors start with an analysis of existing methods, such as Limited Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno (L-BFGS), Fast Gradient Sign Method (FGSM), Jacobian-based Saliency Map Attack (JSMA), Deepfool, Carlini & Wagner attack (C&W), Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN)-based methods and Zeroth-Order Optimization (ZOO). Next, the authors investigate various defensive mechanisms against adversarial attacks, such as adversarial training, gradient masking, defensive distillation, feature squeezing and universal perturbation defence method. Then the authors investigate various works that use adversarial attacks against intrusion and malware detection systems. Next, in [1], M. Ali et al. investigate adversarial attacks against an AI-based IDS, which was trained with the NSL-KDD dataset. In particular, for the detection process, MLP models are utilised, while poisoning adversarial attacks are used to investigate their resilience in terms of Mean Square Error (MSE), Accuracy, Precision and Recall. Similarly, in [14], K. Yang et al. investigate adversarial examples against DL models utilised for intrusion detection. In this case, also NSL-KDD is used, while three black-box attacks are used, namely: (a) C&W-based method, (b) ZOO-based attack and (c) GAN-based attack. Finally, in [13], D. Shu et al. focus on GAN-based adversarial attacks against ML-based IDS. For their experiments, the CIC IDS 2017 dataset was used to train a Variational AutoEncoder (VAE), while active learning is to further optimise the GAN-based attacks.

Figure 1: Architecture of the proposed AI-powered IDS

3 AI-POWERED INTRUSION DETECTION AGAINST IEC 60870-5-104 ATTACKS

As depicted in Fig. 1, the architecture of the proposed AI-powered IDS consists of five modules: (a) Network Traffic Collection Module, (b) IEC-104 Flow Extraction Module, (c) AI Detection Engine and (d) Notification Module. The first module is responsible for capturing the IEC 60870-5-104 network traffic data (i.e., pcap files) in a periodic manner (such as per 30 seconds), taking full advantage of a Switched Port Analyser (SPAN) (i.e., port mirroring) and tcpdump. The IEC-104 Flow Extraction Module refers to a custom flow generator from a previous work [9] that generates bidirectional flow statistics that are related to the application-layer features of IEC 60870-5-104. Next, the AI Detection Engine uses the pre-trained ML/DL models in order to detect the corresponding IEC 60870-5-104 cyberattacks. For the training process, the IEC 60870-5-104 Intrusion Detection Dataset [9] was utilised. This dataset is publicly available in IEEE Dataport and Zenodo. Four AI methods are investigated in the context of AI Detection Engine: (a) Decision Tree, (b) Random Forest, (c) XGBoost, and (d) MLP. The evaluation of these methods is provided in section 5. Finally, the Notification Module generates the corresponding security events.

Figure 2: Workflow and Execution of FGSM and CTGAN Attacks

4 FGSM AND CTGAN ADVERSARIAL ATTACKS

The resilience and accuracy of the proposed AI-powered IDS in terms of its pre-trained ML/DL-based detection models (Decision Tree, Random Forest, XGBOOST, MLP under the umbrella of AI Detection Engine) are examined with two complementary evasion attacks, namely (a) FGSM and (b) CTGAN adversarial attack. As illustrated in Fig. 2, first, FGSM is executed in order to generate an adversarial dataset. Next, this adversarial dataset is to train and generate the CTGAN Adversarial Attack Generator. Finally, both FGSM and CTGAN-based adversarial attacks are used to check the resilience of the previous ML/DL models. In the first case, FGSM (Equation 1) is a gradient-based attack, which takes the original input data and adds a perturbation proportional to the sign of the computed gradients. The perturbation is determined by multiplying the sign of the gradients by a small ϵ value, which controls the magnitude of the perturbation. By multiplying with the sign of the gradients, FGSM ensures that the perturbations are added in the direction that maximizes the loss function. The new data are called adversarial data or examples. The specifics of using evasion attacks on tabular data rely on the dataset’s structure and other characteristics. By changing the value of a single feature or a number of features at once, adversarial examples can be produced. The objective is to create adversarial examples that closely resemble real data points but produce false predictions when fed to the target model. In the context of this work, this attack was implemented through the Adversarial Robustness Toolbox (ART). ART is a Python tool, which can generate a variety of adversarial attacks (such as FGSM, C&W and Projected Gradient Descent (PGD)), including also relevant defensive mechanisms.

$$adv_x = x + \epsilon \cdot \text{sign}(\nabla_x J(\theta, x, y)) \quad (1)$$

where:

$adv_x \rightarrow$ Adversarial data

$x \rightarrow$ Original data

$y \rightarrow$ Original input label

$\epsilon \rightarrow$ Multiplier to ensure the perturbations are small

$\theta \rightarrow$ Model parameters

$J \rightarrow$ Loss function. In our case, the CrossEntropy function (Equation 2)

$$\text{CrossEntropy}(y, \hat{y}) = - \sum_i y_i \log(\hat{y}_i) \quad (2)$$

y represents the true labels or target values, (3)

\hat{y} represents the predicted probabilities or outputs from the model, (4)

i denotes the index of the classes or categories. (5)

CTGAN is a generative model intended to learn and produce synthetic tabular data that closely resembles actual datasets (i.e., the adversarial dataset from ART in our case). It is especially valuable for applications where maintaining the statistical properties and structure of the original data is crucial. As illustrated in Fig. 3,

CTGAN consists of two complementary neural networks: (a) the generator and (b) the discriminator. The generator network seeks to generate synthetic samples that replicate the characteristics of actual data, whereas the discriminator network attempts to differentiate between actual and synthetic samples. The two neural networks are trained through a competitive process in which they continuously learn and improve their capabilities. For this purpose, the binary cross-entropy loss function (Equation 6) is utilised, where y denotes the true binary labels or target values, and \hat{y} implies the predicted probabilities or outputs from the model.

$$\text{BinaryCrossEntropy}(y, \hat{y}) = -(y \log(\hat{y}) + (1 - y) \log(1 - \hat{y})) \quad (6)$$

Figure 3: CTGAN Architecture and Training

The generator is composed of a sequential building block that encapsulates the sequence of operations. Within the sequential building block, there are two residual blocks and a linear layer. Each Residual block follows a similar pattern. The first one starts with a fully connected layer that takes an input of size 128 features and produces an output tensor of size 256. This fully connected layer performs a linear transformation on the input. Subsequently, the output of the fully connected layer is passed through a batch normalisation layer with 256 features. The purpose of batch normalisation is to normalise the output by subtracting the batch mean and dividing it by the batch standard deviation, which aids in stabilising the training process. After batch normalisation, a rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation function (Equation 7, where x represents the input to the ReLU function, $ReLU(x)$ calculates the maximum between 0 and x) is applied, introducing non-linearity and increasing the expressive power of the model. Following the Residual blocks, there is a linear layer, which takes an input of size 640 and produces an output tensor of size 158. Similar to the previous linear layer, it performs another linear transformation on the input. In summary, the generator model takes an input of size 128, applies two Residual blocks with batch normalisation and ReLU activation, and then feeds the output into a final Linear layer. The resulting output size of the generator is 158.

$$\text{ReLU}(x) = \max(0, x) \quad (7)$$

The discriminator consists of a sequence of linear layers, LeakyReLU activations, and dropout layers. The input dimension is multiplied by the `pac` value, which is set to 10, resulting in a `dim` value of $256 \times 10 = 2560$. The discriminator architecture is constructed by iteratively adding layers to the sequence. The first linear layer takes the input of dimension 2560 and outputs a tensor of dimension 256. A LeakyReLU activation function (Equation 8) with a slope of 0.2 is then applied, introducing non-linearity. To prevent overfitting and improve generalization, a dropout layer with a dropout rate of 0.5 is included. The `dim` value is updated to 256 in this case, and the process is repeated for each item in the `discriminator_dim_list`, which contains a single value of 256. Another linear layer transforms the input of dimension 256 to a single output unit, representing the discriminator's final prediction. Overall, the discriminator architecture consists of linear layers with dimensions 2560, 256, and 1, connected by LeakyReLU activations and dropout layers.

$$\text{LeakyReLU}(x) = \begin{cases} x, & \text{if } x \geq 0 \\ \alpha x, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where:

- x : Input value to the activation function
- α : Slope or negative coefficient of the function

5 EVALUATION ANALYSIS

5.1 Datasets and Evaluation Metrics

The IEC 60870-5-104 Intrusion Detection Dataset [9] is used to test the efficiency of the aforementioned AI-powered IDS and the FGSM and CTGAN adversarial attacks. In particular, the `Balanced_IEC104_Train_Test_CSV_files.zip` is used. This zip file includes balanced Comma-Separated Values (CSV) files from `CICFlowMeter` and the IEC-104 Flow Extraction Module (a component of the AI-powered IDS) that could be utilised for training ML and DL methods. The zip file includes different folders for the corresponding flow timeout values for each generator. In this paper, `test_custom_120_test` and `train` files are used. These files include flow statistics related to the following IEC 60870-5-104 attacks: MITM, traffic sniffing, `C_RD_NA_1`, `C_CI_NA_1`, `C_RP_NA_1`, `C_SC_NA_1`, `C_SE_NA_1`, `M_SP_NA_1_DOS`, `C_CI_NA_1_DOS`, `C_SE_NA_1_DOS`, `C_RD_NA_1_DOS`, `C_RP_NA_1_DOS`. On the other hand, the following evaluation metrics are used to test the effectiveness of the proposed AI-powered IDS and the FGSM and CTGAN adversarial attacks.

The metric of accuracy (Equation 9) measures the proportion of correct classifications in relation to the total instances. This evaluation metric is considered appropriate when the training dataset is balanced, meaning it contains an equal number of instances for all classes.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (9)$$

where:

- TP → True Positives
- TN → True Negatives
- FP → False Positives
- FN → False Negatives

TPR (Equation 10) represents the fraction of actual intrusion instances that were correctly identified as intrusions.

$$\text{TPR} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (10)$$

FPR (Equation 11) indicates the proportion of normal instances that were incorrectly classified as cyberattacks, reflecting the balance between the accurate identification of normal instances and the occurrence of false alarms.

$$\text{FPR} = \frac{FP}{FP + FN} \quad (11)$$

The F1 score (Equation 12) is a metric that captures the balance between true positive rate (TPR) and precision. Precision is defined as the ratio of true positives to the sum of true positives and false positives.

$$\text{F1} = \frac{2 \times TP}{2 \times TP + FP + FN} \quad (12)$$

Finally, in order to test the similarity of the data generated by CTGAN and the adversarial dataset (generated by FGSM through ART), the Fréchet Inception Distance (FID) metric and the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) similarity test are used. FID is defined by Equation 13, while the KS test compares the cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of the two samples to assess the similarity between their distributions. The test statistic is the maximum absolute difference (D) between the two CDFs. The null hypothesis of the test assumes that the two samples are drawn from the same distribution.

$$\text{FID} = \|\mu_r - \mu_p\|^2 + \text{tr}(\Sigma_r + \Sigma_p - 2\sqrt{\Sigma_r \cdot \Sigma_p}) \quad (13)$$

where μ_r and μ_p are the vectors of the real and generated data, respectively, while Σ_r and Σ_p are the covariance matrices of the aforementioned vectors. Finally, the term tr denotes the trace of the matrix.

5.2 Experimental Results

The experimental results were carried out with Windows 11 Pro, Intel Core i9-10980XE CPU @ 3.00 GHz, Nvidia, GeForce RTX 3090 GPU, 64GB Random Access Memory (RAM) and 1TB Solid Disk Drive (SSD). First, utilising the IEC 60870-5-104 Intrusion Detection Dataset. Table 1 summarises the experimental results of AI Detection Engine, comparing the detection performance of four ML/DL methods: (a) Decision Tree, XGBOOST, Random Forest and MLP. The best results are achieved by Random Forest where $\text{Accuracy} = 0.8244$, $\text{TPR} = 0.8244$, $\text{FPR} = 0.0159$ and $\text{F1} = 0.8098$. Fig. 4 shows the confusion matrix of Random Forest. On the other side, the worst performance is accomplished by MLP, where $\text{Accuracy} = 0.6908$, $\text{TPR} = 0.6908$, $\text{FPR} = 0.0281$ and $\text{F1} = 0.6852$.

Table 1: Detection Evaluation Results with the IEC 60870-5-104 Intrusion Detection Dataset

ML/DL Method	Accuracy	TPR	FPR	F1
Decision Tree	0.8116	0.8116	0.0171	0.7959
XGBOOST	0.8200	0.8200	0.0163	0.8069
Random Forest	0.8244	0.8244	0.0159	0.8098
MLP	0.6908	0.6908	0.0281	0.6852

Figure 4: Confusion Matrix of Random Forest - AI Detection Engine

Next, using the FGSM method, three ϵ values: $\epsilon = 0.001$, $\epsilon = 0.003$ and $\epsilon = 0.01$ were used to generate the respective adversarial datasets and test how they can affect the detection performance of the aforementioned ML/DL models. Table 2 - Table 3 summarize these experimental results. In particular, when $\epsilon = 0.001$, again the best performance is achieved by Random Forest where Accuracy = 0.7454, TPR = 0.7454, FPR = 0.0231 and F1 = 0.7405. On the other hand, the worst results are accomplished by Decision Tree, where Accuracy = 0.6395, TPR = 0.6395, FPR = 0.0327 and F1 = 0.6382. Next, when $\epsilon = 0.003$, the best performance is achieved by MLP where Accuracy = 0.7052, TPR = 0.7052, FPR = 0.0267 and F1 = 0.6966. On the other hand, the worst results are accomplished by Decision Tree, where Accuracy = 0.5370, TPR = 0.5370, FPR = 0.0420 and F1 = 0.5273. Finally, when $\epsilon = 0.01$, the best performance is achieved by MLP where Accuracy = 0.6933, TPR = 0.6933, FPR = 0.0278 and F1 = 0.6851. On the other hand, the worst results are accomplished by Decision Tree, where Accuracy = 0.3818, TPR = 0.3818, FPR = 0.0561 and F1 = 0.3738. Based on the evaluation results, it seems that Random Forest consistently achieves the highest accuracy, TPR, and F1 score across all three tables. This demonstrates better performance in detecting the FGSM adversarial instances compared to other methods such as Decision Tree, XGBOOST, and MLP. On the other hand, the worst detection results are usually observed with the Decision Tree method, which presents lower accuracy, TPR, F1 score, and higher FPR compared to the other methods in all three tables. There are some variations for each epsilon value. For example, when ϵ

is 0.001, MLP performs better than XGBOOST, but when ϵ is 0.003 and 0.01, XGBOOST outperforms MLP. These differences indicate that the effectiveness of the ML/DL methods may vary depending on the specific characteristics of the FGSM adversarial dataset.

Table 2: Detection Evaluation Results with the FGSM Adversarial Dataset ($\epsilon = 0.001$)

ML/DL Method	Accuracy	TPR	FPR	F1
Decision Tree	0.6395	0.6395	0.0327	0.6382
XGBOOST	0.7095	0.7095	0.0264	0.7072
Random Forest	0.7454	0.7454	0.0231	0.7405
MLP	0.7047	0.7047	0.0268	0.6955

Figure 5: Confusion Matrix of Random Forest with the FGSM Adversarial Dataset ($\epsilon = 0.001$)

Table 3: Detection Evaluation Results with the FGSM Adversarial Dataset ($\epsilon = 0.003$)

ML/DL Method	Accuracy	TPR	FPR	F1
Decision Tree	0.5370	0.5370	0.0420	0.5273
XGBOOST	0.5797	0.5797	0.0382	0.5762
Random Forest	0.6272	0.6272	0.0338	0.6202
MLP	0.7052	0.7052	0.0267	0.6966

Table 4: Detection Evaluation Results with the FGSM Adversarial Dataset ($\epsilon = 0.01$)

ML/DL Method	Accuracy	TPR	FPR	F1
Decision Tree	0.3818	0.3818	0.0561	0.3738
XGBOOST	0.4110	0.4110	0.0535	0.3947
Random Forest	0.4331	0.4331	0.0515	0.4133
MLP	0.6933	0.6933	0.0278	0.6851

Then, the effects of CTGAN adversarial attacks are investigated. In particular, for each adversarial dataset generated by the different values of ϵ in the FGSM method, the corresponding CTGANs are generated. Fig. 7 shows the similarity rate between the adversarial datasets generated by FGSM and the corresponding CTGANs. For this purpose, FID and the KS similarity test are used. Table 5 shows the detection performance when CTGAN is trained with the FGSM adversarial dataset with $\epsilon = 0.001$. MLP achieves the best performance with Accuracy = 0.2464, TPR = 0.2361, FPR = 0.0683, and F1 = 0.2378. On the other side, XGBOOST presents the worst performance with Accuracy = 0.1745, TPR = 0.1942, FPR = 0.0735, and F1 = 0.1756. Moving to Table 6, it showcases the detection performance when CTGAN is trained with the FGSM adversarial dataset with $\epsilon = 0.003$. Random Forest achieves the best performance with Accuracy = 0.2918, TPR = 0.2495, FPR = 0.0642, and F1 = 0.2425. Similarly, XGBOOST accomplishes the worst performance with Accuracy = 0.2447, TPR = 0.2225, FPR = 0.0691, and F1 = 0.2093. Finally, Table 7 presents the detection performance when CTGAN is trained with the FGSM adversarial dataset, using $\epsilon = 0.01$. MLP achieves the best performance with Accuracy = 0.2687, TPR = 0.2490, FPR = 0.0665, and F1 = 0.2429, while XGBOOST achieved the worst performance with Accuracy = 0.2272, TPR = 0.2225, FPR = 0.0699, and F1 = 0.2066. In summary, the Random Forest and MLP models generally show stronger performance than Decision Tree and XGBoost across varying epsilon values. However, the performance of all methods depends on the specific ϵ value, indicating a need for method-specific tuning for different levels of adversarial robustness in the CTGAN datasets.

Figure 6: Confusion Matrix of Random Forest with the CTGAN Dataset (eps = 0.001)

According to the experimental results, the Decision Tree model performs better on the FGSM dataset than on the CTGAN dataset at all levels of ϵ (0.001, 0.003, and 0.01). The accuracy, TPR, and F1 scores are consistently higher for the FGSM adversarial datasets. Similarly, the XGBOOST model shows better performance on the FGSM adversarial datasets compared to the CTGAN datasets across all ϵ levels. The Random Forest model also performs better on the FGSM dataset at all ϵ levels. The performance difference between

Table 5: Detection Evaluation Results with the CTGAN Dataset (eps = 0.001)

ML/DL Method	Accuracy	TPR	FPR	F1
Decision Tree	0.2206	0.2148	0.0702	0.2119
XGBOOST	0.1745	0.1942	0.0735	0.1756
Random Forest	0.2281	0.2337	0.0693	0.2169
MLP	0.2464	0.2505	0.0683	0.2378

Table 6: Detection Evaluation Results with the CTGAN Dataset (eps = 0.003)

ML/DL Method	Accuracy	TPR	FPR	F1
Decision Tree	0.2660	0.2285	0.0671	0.2299
XGBOOST	0.2447	0.2127	0.0691	0.2093
Random Forest	0.2918	0.2495	0.0642	0.2425
MLP	0.2545	0.2361	0.0676	0.2275

Table 7: Detection Evaluation Results with the CTGAN Dataset (eps = 0.01)

ML/DL Method	Accuracy	TPR	FPR	F1
Decision Tree	0.2502	0.2457	0.0676	0.2243
XGBOOST	0.2272	0.2225	0.0699	0.2066
Random Forest	0.2541	0.2422	0.0676	0.2223
MLP	0.2687	0.2490	0.0665	0.2429

Figure 7: Similarity Rate between FGSM Adversarial Datasets and CTGAN Datasets

the two cases is more prominent in this case. Finally, also the MLP model shows a similar trend as the other models. It performs better on the FGSM adversarial dataset across all ϵ levels. However, the performance gap between the FGSM and CTGAN datasets is less pronounced for the MLP compared to the other models, especially at higher ϵ values. In summary, all models tested (Decision Tree, XGBOOST, Random Forest, and MLP) perform better on the FGSM

adversarial dataset compared to the CTGAN dataset at all tested levels of ϵ . However, the difference in performance is less noticeable for the MLP model, especially at higher levels of ϵ . This could potentially indicate that the MLP model is more robust to noise or more capable of handling the specific features or distribution of the CTGAN datasets.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Despite the fact that the rapid evolution of the smart technologies results in several benefits in the lifecycle of the smart electrical grid, it also raises severe cybersecurity issues. In this paper, we focus our attention on the power of AI. On the one hand, AI can contribute significantly to the detection of cyberattacks and anomalies against IEC 60870-5-104, an industrial protocol which is utilised widely in the energy sector in Europe. However, on the other side, AI can also be used to trick the AI-enabled intrusion detection, thus leading to devastating consequences. In particular, in this paper, first, we implemented an AI-powered IDPS for the IEC 60870-5-104 protocol, utilising four ML/DL methods: (a) Decision Tree, (b) Random Forest, (c) XGBOOST and (d) MLP. Next, we use the FGSM method in order to evaluate the resilience of the previous methods under the conditions of a typical adversarial attack. Finally, given the FGSM adversarial datasets, we implement a CTGAN adversarial attack generator. In general, the performance of the tested models (Decision Tree, XGBOOST, Random Forest, and MLP) is better on the FGSM adversarial datasets when compared to the CTGAN datasets. However, the difference in performance is less distinct for the MLP model, particularly at higher epsilon levels. This observation suggests that the MLP method might be more resilient to noise or better equipped to handle the specific characteristics or distribution of the CTGAN datasets. To conclude, our future plans aim to investigate more complicated adversarial attacks and evaluate relevant countermeasures in order to strengthen and optimise the resilience of the AI security models.

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